

GEMINI

GREENING EUROPEAN MOBILITY
through cascading innovation INITIATIVES

D2.2: MLLs User Acceptance Tests Templates

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronyms	Full meaning
B2B	Business-to-Business
CIM	Common Impact Model
MaaS	Mobility-as-a-Service
MLL	Mobility Living Lab
NMS	New and Shared Mobility Services
UTAUT2	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, version 2

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents a set of user acceptance tools and guidelines for the GEMINI new and shared mobility services (NMS). These tools deliver a user centric approach to ensure design and implementation of successful business models for the GEMINI NMS.

The deliverable reviews existing technology user acceptance models, notably the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2) and integrates social acceptance theories to outline factors influencing NMS adoption.

Furthermore, the Common Impact Model (CIM) methodology is introduced for assessing user and stakeholder acceptance across project phases. The model has been tailored to fit mobility solutions specific to GEMINI. Last, this deliverable provides several tools and templates for user acceptance, aiming to guide the GEMINI mobility living labs (MLLs) in the design and implementation of NMS effectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

The GEMINI project develops and tests sustainable business models for New and Shared Mobility Services (NMS). Ultimately, the success of these business models relies on end-users' approval and readiness to sustainably adopt the new mobility options. Early prediction of end-users' behaviour supports evaluations of different designs and helps avoiding pitfalls in the implementation process (Osswald et al., 2012).

The objective of this deliverable is to provide to GEMINI NMS a set of guidelines and tools for considering user and community acceptance throughout their design and implementation. The tools are both qualitative and quantitative (surveys, stakeholder mapping, co-design processes) and were adapted to the GEMINI design framework to address mobility sector acceptance challenges and behavioural innovation needs.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of research on user and community acceptance of NMS. It starts by introducing the concepts of user and community acceptance. These concepts are then used as a framework for mapping factors that influence acceptance of new mobility solutions identified through a literature review. The purpose of this literature review is to provide guidelines on relevant factors to address when developing strategies to evaluate and enhance user acceptance of the NMS.

In chapter 3, a methodology for considering user and community acceptance at each phase of the GEMINI project is presented: the Common Impact Model (CIM). CIM is a methodology to facilitate community acceptance of new technical solutions, originally designed in the E-LAND project in the context of establishing decarbonized multi-vector local energy systems (Petrovich et al., 2021). In GEMINI, the CIM methodology will be adapted to the GEMINI design framework to address user aspects of mobility behaviour.

Finally, in chapter 4, the user acceptance test templates are presented. These templates are tools that the GEMINI mobility living labs (MLLs) can use to explore and evaluate user acceptance. Following the CIM, different templates are provided for each of the steps of the project.

2 ACCEPTANCE OF NEW AND SHARED MOBILITY SOLUTIONS OR SERVICES

2.1 Introduction

User acceptance of new innovations has been extensively researched, especially in the field of information systems and technology. Various theories and models have been developed to map factors that influence adoption and use of new technologies, e.g., the Technology Acceptance Model, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, and Innovation Diffusion Model (Alshammari & Rosli, 2020). Many of these models draw from psychological theories that have been developed to explain behaviour in a broad sense, such as Theory of Reasoned Action and Theory of Planned Behaviour (Taherdoost, 2018).

User acceptance of new mobility services has also often been viewed through the lens of technology acceptance models (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023). This is because new mobility services, such as shared mobility and mobility as a service, combine new technologies with new and existing business models (Slowik & Kamakaté, 2017).

In this deliverable, the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology V2 (UTAUT2) (Venkatesh et al., 2012) is used as a framework to map factors that influence user acceptance of new mobility solutions. UTAUT2 is the latest development in the field of technology acceptance models and by 2021 had already accumulated more than 6000 citations (Tamilmani et al., 2021). It has been applied in various contexts, among others in understanding acceptance of new mobility solutions, such as automated public transportation, car-sharing, and bike-sharing (Jahanshahi et al., 2020). UTAUT2 is presented in detail in section 2.2.1.

However, technology acceptance research has been criticized for its individualistic focus and limited consideration of the social context of technology use (Tabourdeau & Grange, 2020). Research on social acceptance has typically taken a much broader approach. For example, Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) define three dimensions of social acceptance: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance, and market acceptance.

Thus, in this deliverable UTAUT2's definition of social influence is enriched with insights from social acceptance literature. In section 2.2.2, we discuss these models of social acceptance. Finally, section 2.3 presents an overview of drivers of new and shared mobility solutions' acceptance, combining insights from both models of acceptance and literature on acceptance of new and shared mobility solutions specifically.

2.2 Models of acceptance

2.2.1 Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology V2

Development of UTAUT stemmed from the observation that research on technology acceptance had resulted in several, partially overlapping theoretical models (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In their research, Venkatesh et al. (2003) identified eight commonly used theories/models of technology use: the theory of reasoned action, the technology acceptance model, the motivational model, the theory of planned behaviour, a model combining the technology acceptance model and the theory of planned behaviour, the model of PC utilization, the innovation diffusion theory, and the social cognitive theory. They reviewed and empirically compared these eight models and formulated the UTAUT based on conceptual and empirical similarities across the models.

In 2012, the model was extended into a version 2 (UTAUT2) (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Venkatesh et al. (2012) wanted to develop the model with a specific consideration for consumer use context,

as the original model had been originally designed to explain employee technology acceptance and use.

UTAUT2 identifies seven key constructs that influence behavioural intention to use a technology and/or technology use (Venkatesh et al., 2012):

- **Performance expectancy:** perceived usefulness and efficiency
- **Effort expectancy:** perceived ease of use, user-friendliness
- **Social influence:** impact of peers, social networks, and societal norms
- **Facilitating conditions:** support systems and resources available to users
- **Hedonic motivation:** the fun, enjoyment, or pleasure derived from using a technology
- **Price value:** trade-off between the perceived benefits of the solutions and the monetary cost for using it
- **Habit**

Additionally, individual difference variables, namely age, gender, and experience are theorized to moderate various UTAUT2 relationships (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

UTAUT2 has been widely used to understand acceptance of different technologies in various user populations and cultural settings (Tamilmani et al., 2021). In the context of transportation services, UTAUT has been used in the fields of automated public transportation, car-sharing, and bike-sharing (Jahanshahi et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Models of social acceptance

Technology acceptance models, such as UTAUT2, have been criticized for their narrow view on the social context surrounding technology use (Tabourdeau & Grange, 2020). For example, UTAUT2 defines social influence on technology use as “the extent to which consumers perceive that important others (e.g., family and friends) believe they should use a particular technology” (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Other fields, such as environmental studies, have taken a broader approach (Tabourdeau & Grange, 2020). In this deliverable, insights from these disciplines are used to enrich UTAUT2’s definition of social influence in technology acceptance.

Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) distinguish three dimensions of social acceptance: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance and market acceptance. All these dimensions are relevant to the social acceptance of new and shared mobility services and solutions.

Socio-political acceptance is defined as the broadest level of acceptance: general approval by policymakers, regulators, and the wider public (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). This dimension involves legislation, governmental policies, and the overall societal endorsement of an initiative.

Community acceptance, on the other hand, is centred on the local level and involves the specific attitudes and reactions of local communities where the project or technology is being implemented (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). This includes considerations of how a new development will impact the daily lives, environment, and economy of the local populace. Projects that are likely to affect community resources or require changes in local infrastructure often need to address community concerns to ensure successful implementation.

Market acceptance deals with the commercial and economic viability of a technology or innovation (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). This dimension is concerned with whether businesses, investors, and consumers adopt and support a new product or service in the market.

Research on social acceptance also distinguishes between **passive and active acceptance** (Petrovich et al., 2021). Passive acceptance refers to the positive appraisal of the solution, whereby local stakeholders give one-off support to the project and do not oppose it, while their behaviour is not affected by the project. Active acceptance refers to the willingness to actively support the solutions and also change their behaviour to support the project, e.g., starting to use a NMS.

2.3 Factors that influence acceptance of new and shared mobility solutions

2.3.1 Performance expectancy

Performance expectancy refers to users' perception of the technology's usefulness, i.e., how well it aids users in performing tasks more effectively (Venkatesh et al., 2012). It has been shown to be the strongest predictor of intention to use a technology across various contexts (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In the context of shared mobility, performance expectancy encompasses perceptions of the utility of the service as a transportation mode, including its effectiveness in providing quick and comfortable access to destinations.

Research shows that convenience is a significant motivator for adopting micromobility services. Bike-sharing users prioritize services that save time, offer easy access, and provide flexible commuting options (Fishman, 2016). Micromobility solutions, particularly effective for shorter, 'last-mile' urban journeys, appeal to those who seek to bridge gaps in traditional transportation networks (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023).

Interestingly, in the case of (electric) car-sharing services, several studies have found that performance expectancy positively affects behavioural intention to use the services, but to a lesser extent compared to other UTAUT literature (Curtale et al., 2021). Curtale et al. (2021) suggest that one explanation for this could be that people might perceive that other transportation alternatives can reach similar levels of performance as electric car-sharing, and thus other aspects become more important drivers of intention to use.

The role of convenience in performance expectancy extends beyond mere utility. It encompasses the comfort level relative to other modes of transport, the ability to bypass traffic congestion, and overall time efficiency (Elmashhara et al., 2022). Mobility apps, especially Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) platforms, can provide users real time information about pros and cons of using different routes and travel modes, helping users to make a more informed choice of transportation modes based on their needs and preferences (Casquero Soler et al., 2022). Moreover, the reliability of these systems, encompassing aspects like the availability and proper functioning of bicycles, also plays a crucial role in shaping users' decisions to use these services (Pan et al., 2022).

It is important to note that performance expectancy is influenced by effort expectancy, i.e. ease of use. Fleury et al. (2017) observed that people tend to consider car-sharing service as useful if it was easy to use. If a service is not easy to use or requires effort to understand, it's likely to be judged as unuseful.

Suggestions for leveraging performance expectancy:

- Ensure that the vehicles are well-maintained and available in sufficient numbers and locations to meet the demand and expectations of users.
- Provide clear and timely information about the availability, location, and functional status of the vehicles through apps, websites, or other channels.

- If possible, provide information about the NMS's efficiency compared to other modes of traffic, preferably in real time.

2.3.2 Effort expectancy

Effort expectancy refers to the perceived ease of using a system and is an important driver of technology acceptance (Venkatesh et al., 2012). In shared mobility contexts, this translates to user-friendliness and accessibility of both the vehicles and the apps and other tools required for using them. On a wider scale, using shared mobility frees users from the effort associated with owning vehicles, such as responsibility for maintenance and repair, and incurring the full cost of the vehicle (Moeller & Wittkowski, 2010). On the other hand, using shared vehicles can also require more effort than driving a personal vehicle due to service complexity (e.g., having to book a vehicle in advance and define pick-up and return times) or unreliability (e.g., booked vehicle isn't functional) (Hazée et al., 2017).

The user interface of the NMS application is a crucial factor in determining effort expectancy, as it can facilitate or hinder the users' ability to sign up for the service and book and pay for trips. For example, long sign-up procedure has been found to decrease the likelihood of adoption of shared bicycles and other micromobility solutions (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023; Elmashhara et al., 2022). In the case of MaaS, the clarity of interface has been shown to influence the individuals' decision on adoption (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023). Additionally, ease of use of the vehicles' key functionalities, such as systems for locking and unlocking them, can also be important facilitators or barriers for use. It is imperative for providers to design systems that are intuitive and easy to use, considering the varied technological skills and experiences of potential users. Simplifying the process of using shared transport services can enhance their appeal and lead to greater adoption.

Additionally, accessibility of shared mobility services, including the availability of vehicles near potential users, plays a pivotal role in influencing their adoption decisions. Research shows that proximity to shared bicycles, car-sharing stations, and available shared cars significantly affects individuals' intention to use them (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023; Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021).

Suggestions for leveraging effort expectancy:

- Provide users with clear and simple information about the availability and accessibility of the NMS in local language.
- Design the NMS interface and features in a user-friendly and intuitive way, so that users can easily navigate and use the system without much effort or frustration.
- Ensure that there is enough supply of vehicles to meet the demand, and that the vehicles are strategically located in places where people are likely to use them, such as near transit hubs, workplaces, residential areas, or popular destinations.
- Monitor and adjust the supply and distribution of vehicles based on real-time data and user feedback, to optimize the efficiency and effectiveness of the service.

2.3.3 Social influence

Social influence is a pivotal factor in shaping individuals' decisions regarding the adoption of new technical solutions (Venkatesh et al., 2012). In the context of shared mobility, social influence pertains to the impact of peers, social networks, societal norms, and rules and regulations on an individual's decision to embrace NMS. These social aspects are discussed here on three levels: individual, community, and socio-political level, following Wüstenhagen et al. (2007). The importance of all these levels in shared mobility adoption is evident in research.

Individual level

Alshammari and Rosli (2020) emphasize that individuals often turn to their social circles for recommendations and validation when considering the use of new technologies, including shared mobility systems. For example, research has shown that the opinions, experiences, and recommendations of friends and family play a significant role in shaping one's attitude toward bicycle sharing systems, affecting intention to use them (Jahanshahi et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2022). A study in the Netherlands found that people who have colleagues, friends, or family who use electric car-sharing have a higher behavioural intention to use such services themselves (Curtale et al., 2021).

Shared vehicles are also inherently social in the sense that they are shared with other people. This brings up questions of contamination and responsibility. Contamination related to the vehicle being used by other, typically unknown individuals, whereas responsibility refers to concerns about being held accountable for others' usage of the vehicle (Hazée et al., 2017).

Community level

Implementation of a NMS can significantly impact the daily lives, environment, and economy of the local people or community surround the solution. GEMINI D1.1 highlighted some of the positive and negative impacts NMS can have on the communities they are implemented in. On the positive side, NMS typically use more environmentally friendly vehicles and make more intensive use of vehicles, lowering emissions and congestion. More intensive use of the vehicles also releases parking space for other purposes. NMS can also facilitate access to resources and services through increased access to vehicles and transit stations. Typical challenges include safety issues, especially related to micromobility, as well as disturbance caused by incorrect parking and even vandalism of free-floating vehicles. Distributional justice (how are costs and benefits of the NMS shared) and procedural justice (was the decision-making process fair, did all relevant stakeholders have an opportunity to participate) are important factors that influence community acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007).

Both passive and active acceptance of the NMS in the community are important for its long-term viability and social sustainability. To foster both types of acceptance, it is essential to involve the community in the planning and design of the NMS, and address their needs, preferences, and concerns. This can increase trust, legitimacy, and ownership of the NMS among the potential users and stakeholders.

Fishman (2016) highlights that shared mobility programs often incorporate community building and shared experiences, which can enhance their attractiveness and promote adoption. These aspects foster a sense of community and belonging among users, which can be a strong motivator for participation and continued use of shared mobility services. Cooperative car-sharing, where a car is owned and used collectively within a local group such as friends, neighbours, or a nonprofit organization, is typically characterized by communal interest rather than profit motive (Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021).

Socio-political level

Socio-political acceptance refers to the broadest, most general level of acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). Socio-political acceptance of shared mobility services is reflected for example in the European Commission's Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy, which promotes a shift towards more sustainable transport modes, including shared mobility.

Regulation can play a key role in facilitating or hindering the adoption of NMS. GEMINI D1.1 reported that legal and regulatory frameworks have lagged behind the advancement of NMS and described regulatory delay as a major obstacle to achieving the full benefits of shared mobility.

The deliverable also notes that in this context, local authorities have become important actors in setting the rules for shared mobility and that different cities have taken varied approaches to address concerns related to space utilization (e.g., parking, areas where use of micromobility solutions is allowed) and safety (e.g., speed limits, disabling use of micromobility during nighttime).

Public policy and citywide initiatives are also important because they can exert social pressure on individuals to embrace shared mobility options. Brecht et al. (2022) highlight that government-supported campaigns and societal movements emphasizing sustainability and shared transport can influence individuals' decisions to shift from private cars to shared mobility.

Suggestions for leveraging social influences:

- Involve local stakeholders and potential end-users of the NMS from the very beginning of the project through involvement activities. (Practical recommendations for doing this can be found in chapter 0).
- Encourage users to share their positive experiences and feedback in physical community meetings, on social media platforms and online communities.
- Create incentives and rewards for users who refer their friends or family members to use NMS, such as discounts, free rides, or loyalty points.
- Organise events and campaigns that showcase the benefits and advantages of NMS. These events can also provide opportunities for potential users to try out NMS and interact with existing users and service providers.
- Develop partnerships and collaborations with local organizations, such as schools, workplaces, or community groups, that can promote NMS among their members and encourage them to use these services.
- Leverage relevant influencers and opinion leaders who can endorse NMS.
- Engage with relevant stakeholders, such as policymakers, regulators, transport authorities, or industry associations, to raise awareness and understanding of the benefits and impacts of NMS, solve challenges, and advocate for favourable regulations and policies that support the implementation and expansion of NMS.

2.3.4 Facilitating conditions

Facilitating conditions, as defined by Venkatesh et al. (2012), refer to the perceived technical and organizational infrastructure that supports the use of a specific system or technology. In the shared mobility context, this encompasses the support systems and resources available to users, which are critical in influencing their decision to adopt these services. In this deliverable, the concept of facilitating conditions is also extended to the physical environment where the new mobility and shared solutions are implemented, including infrastructure, landscape, and weather conditions.

Support in starting to use the NMS is particularly crucial for novice users or those less familiar with new and shared mobility solutions. It can mitigate potential barriers and ensure that individuals, regardless of their technological proficiency, can comfortably engage with shared mobility services. For example, in the context of B2B car-sharing in France, (Fleury et al., 2017) found that tutorial videos, training and easy access to service provider were motivating factors, especially for first time users.

Acceptance of micromobility solutions can especially be influenced by the environment where the solution is implemented. Several studies have indicated that infrastructural quality, such as pavement conditions and cycling lanes, as well as external factors like weather and air quality influence user intentions to engage with micromobility options (Elmashhara et al., 2022).

Policy and regulatory frameworks were already discussed in relation to social influences, but they can also be viewed as facilitating conditions. Studies by Elmashhara et al. (2022) suggest that favourable government policies, subsidies for users, and well-defined regulatory frameworks can significantly boost the adoption of shared mobility solutions by providing a conducive and supportive environment. On the other hand, factors that make car ownership difficult and more expensive, such as scarcity of parking space, have been found to increase demand of car-sharing (Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021a). Subsidies to support shared mobility on one hand (lower taxes, free parking etc), and policy instruments to lower individual ownership (registration costs, toll roads, etc) on the other can will increase uptake of NMS.

Suggestions for leveraging facilitating conditions:

- Offer adequate support and guidance in the form of tutorials, training, and easy access to customer service.
- Advocate for improving the infrastructure quality, subsidies and incentives for users, and establishing clear and consistent regulatory frameworks.
- Provide clarity on any benefits for the users in terms of shared versus individual ownership, and provide details on current or future policy related opportunities relating to the solution.

2.3.5 Hedonic motivation

Hedonic motivation pertains to the fun, enjoyment, or pleasure derived from using a technology. Venkatesh et al. (2012) incorporated this concept into the extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2), recognizing its significance in influencing consumer behaviour and technology adoption, particularly in consumer contexts.

In the realm of shared mobility solutions, hedonic motivation refers to the enjoyment and satisfaction users derive from using these services. For instance, the leisurely experience of riding an electric bike or the convenience and thrill of using a scooter for urban travel can be significant motivators. Jahanshahi et al. (2020) suggest that the experiential and enjoyable aspects of bicycle sharing systems can significantly impact users' attitudes and their intention to use such services. Additionally, Elmashhara et al. (2022) highlight that the enjoyment users find in the ease of use, the adventure of exploring new areas, or the simple pleasure of outdoor activities can influence their decision to engage with micromobility options.

Gamification is another strategy to leverage hedonic motivation to increase user engagement. Gamification strategies, such as points, leader boards, achievements, badges, feedback, goals, and narratives have been successfully used in different mobility applications (Pasca et al., 2021).

Suggestions for leveraging hedonic motivation:

- Design the service with aesthetic appeal and personalization, such as using attractive colours, logos, or slogans, or allowing users to customize their preferences, settings, or profiles.
- Providing fun and educational content or features, such as trivia, facts, or tips related to the service, the destination, or the environment.
- Provide motivational content or trackers on the usage of the solution over time, related to the preference of the user; such as kilometres cycled or CO₂ saved.
- Gamify the service by e.g. introducing challenges, competitions, or leaderboards among users, or rewarding users for achieving certain goals, such as reducing emissions, saving money, or exploring new areas.

2.3.6 Price value

Price value relates to users' perception of the benefits of the service against the monetary costs of it. Price value significantly influences the adoption of shared mobility solutions. The perceived economic advantages, combined with the broader value proposition, play a vital role in shaping users' decisions.

Price-value and price sensitivity are typical research topics in the context of new and shared mobility solutions. Fishman (2016) identified saving money as a key motivator for bike-sharing use, highlighting the economic appeal of these services as an alternative to more expensive transportation modes. Elmashhara et al. (2022) also emphasize the role of perceived cost-effectiveness in user adoption decisions in the context of shared micromobility solutions.

However, findings on individuals' financial motivations to use car-sharing are mixed (Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021a). While some research shows that users appreciate cost savings achieved through car-sharing services, others have found that cost reduction did not motivate car-sharing use and that people with high income are more likely to use car-sharing services.

Evaluating the cost of using a private versus shared vehicle can be challenging to consumers. Research has indicated that consumers tend to underestimate the true cost of private car ownership (Andor et al., 2020). These costs include not only the initial purchase price but also ongoing costs such as insurance, maintenance, fuel, registration fees, taxes, depreciation, and potential repairs.

Furthermore, price value in shared mobility extends beyond just the monetary aspect to encompass the overall value proposition offered by these services (van Brecht et al., 2022). This includes convenience, time savings, environmental benefits, and technological advancements, which users evaluate against the costs to determine the overall perceived value.

Suggestions for leveraging price value:

- Provide incentives and rewards for new, frequent, and/or loyal users of shared mobility services, such as discounts, coupons, or free rides.
- Offer benefits based on the preferred incentive of the user to recruit new users.
- Offer flexible pricing schemes that cater to different user segments and preferences, such as pay-per-use, subscription, or membership models.
- Educate consumers about the true cost of private vehicle ownership and highlight the potential savings from using shared mobility services.
- Highlight the non-monetary aspects of value, such as convenience, time savings, environmental benefits, and technological advancements, by improving the availability, accessibility, reliability, and quality of shared mobility services.

2.3.7 Habit

Habit, as a factor in the acceptance and use of technology, particularly within shared mobility solutions, refers to the degree to which people tend to perform behaviours automatically due to learning. This concept, as elaborated by Venkatesh et al. (2012) in the UTAUT2, acknowledges that habitual use of a technology significantly influences its continued use. Habit forms through repeated use and is characterized by behaviours that become automatic over time.

Schikofsky et al. (2020) observed that people tend to compare the new travel behaviours with their habitual ones in the process of adoption. Several studies have also shown that people who are familiar with car rental programs are more likely to use car-sharing (Nansubuga &

Kowalkowski, 2021a). In the context of MaaS, people with experience of car-sharing and/or multimodal platforms were more likely to use MaaS solutions (Maas, 2022).

Suggestions for leveraging habits:

- Design interventions that target existing habits and provide cues to trigger new behaviours. For example, offering incentives or reminders to use shared mobility options at specific times or locations that match users' existing travel patterns.

2.3.8 Additional factors

Besides the factors that UTAUT2 defines as influences on acceptance of new technologies, research on new and shared mobility solutions has identified additional factors that can be relevant in that context. These factors are;

Perceived safety has been identified as a key construct in the context of mobility due to its significance in especially micromobility, but also transportation more broadly. Users' perceptions of their physical safety while using shared mobility services, such as bike-sharing systems, significantly influence their willingness to adopt these modes of transport (Fishman, 2016; Jahanshahi et al., 2020). Addressing safety concerns, through measures like improved cycling infrastructure, enhanced vehicle safety features, and clear safety guidelines, is crucial in fostering user trust and adoption of shared mobility solutions.

Perceived environmental benefits have also been identified as a driver of acceptance for new shared mobility solutions. Elmashhara et al. (2022) showed that consumers are increasingly aware of the environmental impacts of their transportation choices. In their study on the acceptance of electric bicycle-sharing systems, Pan et al. (2022) indicated that users' recognition of the environmental benefits of electric bicycles, such as reduced emissions and sustainable urban mobility, can positively influence their adoption. Other studies have found that people who are more concerned about the environment are more likely to use shared bicycles, shared electric scooters and MaaS (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023). Nansubuga and Kowalkowski's (2021) review showed that environmental consciousness may be one key driver for car-sharing use, but not sufficient alone.

Health benefits have emerged as influential factors in the acceptance of new and shared mobility solutions and services. Promoting a healthier lifestyle has been identified as one driver for adopting shared bicycle services (Elmashhara et al., 2022).

Trust in addition to safety and security trust has been identified as a main factors influencing people's attitudes to NMS (Launonen, et al., 2021). Positive real-life experiences with new and innovative mobility solutions, as well as relevant information from peers and the media are found to diminish negative preconceptions and distrust to change subjective norms.

Technological advancements play a crucial role in shaping the user experience and acceptance of shared mobility solutions. The integration of advanced technologies, such as GPS tracking, mobile applications for easy access and payment, and the incorporation of smart, connected features in vehicles, enhances user convenience and attractiveness of these services. As outlined by Alshammari & Rosli (2020), the continual evolution of technology in shared mobility systems can influence user perceptions of ease of use and functionality, thereby impacting adoption.

2.3.9 Moderating factors

UTAUT2 suggests that individual difference variables, namely age, gender, and experience moderate various UTAUT2 relationships (Venkatesh et al., 2012). In practice this means that the

end-users age, gender, and level of experience may influence how strong of an effect the previously discussed factors have on their acceptance of NMS.

Zhang & Kamargianni (2023) highlight that **socio-demographic factors** significantly impact the acceptance of new shared mobility services. **Age**, for instance, has a strong influence, with younger individuals showing more interest in and likelihood of adopting micromobility (Elmashhara et al., 2022) and MaaS packages (Maas, 2022). However, findings related to the impact of **gender** on micromobility and MaaS acceptance are mixed, indicating that gender may influence adoption in varied ways depending on the specific context or type of service offered (Zhang & Kamargianni, 2023). Men have been found to be more likely to use car-sharing services (Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021).

In technology acceptance models like the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), **experience** is frequently considered a moderating factor. Experienced users might be more adept at navigating the systems, have established habits, and developed specific expectations about the services. For shared mobility solutions, users with more experience in using these services might have different perceptions and acceptance levels compared to novice users (see e.g. Maas 2022; Nansubuga & Kowalkowski, 2021).

2.4 Conclusion

This chapter presented different models of acceptance for technology use, focusing on the UTAUT2 and the models of social acceptance. UTAUT2 is a model that identifies seven key constructs that influence behavioural intention and/or technology use, and considers the moderating effects of individual difference variables. UTAUT2 has been applied to various technologies and settings, including new and shared mobility services such as automated public transportation, car-sharing, and bike-sharing.

However, technology acceptance research has been criticized for its individualistic focus and limited consideration of the social context of technology use (Tabourdeau & Grange, 2020). Research on social acceptance has typically taken a much broader approach and distinguishes three dimensions: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance, and market acceptance. These dimensions capture the general approval of policymakers, regulators, and the public; the specific attitudes and reactions of local communities; and the commercial and economic viability of a technology or innovation, respectively. Social acceptance also involves the distinction between passive and active acceptance, which refers to the level of support and behavioural change that local stakeholders exhibit towards a project or technology.

Furthermore, different factors that influence acceptance of new and shared mobility solutions were presented in this chapter such as: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, price value, habit, moderating factors such as age and experience, and other factors such as safety and trust. For each type of factor, suggestions for leveraging them are presented and summarised in the table below:

Table 1 Summary of factors and suggested intervention for user acceptance

Factor category	Intervention
Effort Expectancy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide users with clear and simple information about the availability and accessibility of the NMS in local language. • Design the NMS interface and features in a user-friendly and intuitive way, so that users can easily navigate and use the system without much effort or frustration. • Ensure that there is enough supply of vehicles to meet the demand, and that the vehicles are strategically located in places where people are likely to use them. • Monitor and adjust the supply and distribution of vehicles based on real-time data and user feedback.
Social Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve local stakeholders and potential end-users of the NMS from the very beginning of the project through involvement activities. • Encourage users to share their positive experiences and feedback. Create incentives and rewards for users who refer their friends or family members to use NMS. • Organise events and campaigns that showcase the benefits and advantages of NMS. • Develop partnerships and collaborations with local organizations. Leverage relevant influencers and opinion leaders who can endorse NMS. • Engage with relevant stakeholders to raise awareness and understanding of the benefits and impacts of NMS.
Facilitating Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer adequate support and guidance in the form of tutorials, training, and easy access to customer service. • Advocate for improving the infrastructure quality, subsidies and incentives for users, and establishing clear and consistent regulatory frameworks. • Provide clarity on any benefits for the users in terms of shared versus individual ownership, and provide details on current or future policy related opportunities relating to the solution.
Hedonic Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design the service with aesthetic appeal and personalization. Providing fun and educational content or features. • Provide motivational content or trackers on the usage of the solution over time. • Gamify the service by introducing challenges, competitions, or leaderboards among users, or rewarding users for achieving certain goals.
Price Value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide incentives and rewards for new, frequent, and/or loyal users of shared mobility services. • Offer benefits based on the preferred incentive of the user to recruit new users. • Offer flexible pricing schemes that cater to different user segments and preferences. • Educate consumers about the true cost of private vehicle ownership and highlight the potential savings from using shared mobility services.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Highlight the non-monetary aspects of value, such as convenience, time savings, environmental benefits, and technological advancements.
Habit	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Design interventions that target existing habits and provide cues to trigger new behaviours. For example, offering incentives or reminders to use shared mobility options at specific times or locations that match users' existing travel patterns.

The theoretical framework outlined here was presented to all GEMINI MLLs during a workshop in Amsterdam, with a goal of co-creating a good framework for linking MLL goals with relevant intervention and evaluation methods. The links between MLL KPIs, user intervention methods and evaluation plans were explored, and Living Labs were together creating solutions for engagement strategies with intervention addressing the acceptance needs for the particular solution or service.

3 FRAMEWORK FOR CONSIDERING USER ACCEPTANCE THROUGHOUT GEMINI: COMMON IMPACT MODEL

3.1 Introduction to Common Impact Model

The Common Impact Model (CIM) is a methodology to facilitate community acceptance of new technical solutions (Petrovich et al., 2021). It provides both a process and practical tools for considering and facilitating acceptance throughout the design and implementation of a solution. CIM was originally designed in the E-LAND project in the context of establishing decarbonized multi-vector local energy systems (Petrovich et al., 2021). The model has also been applied in the context of energy renovations in the Horizon Europe project FORTESIE. In GEMINI, the CIM methodology will be adapted to the GEMINI design framework to address user aspects of mobility behaviour throughout the design and operation of the MLLs.

Both the CIM and the GEMINI co-design and deployment process, defined in the grant agreement, advocate for a bottom-up approach, where the service design process starts from developing an in-depth understanding of the community's/customer's needs and context, and proceeds with iterative development and testing to ensure that the solution fits the end-users needs and preferences. Finally, the CIM advocates for developing a strategy to facilitate long-term acceptance of the solution. Thus, the GEMINI co-design and deployment process's steps are compatible with CIM and can be mapped against the CIM phases, as presented in Figure 1.

For the purposes of GEMINI, the CIM and the associated tools have been modified to better account for the acceptance of new and shared mobility solutions and match the design thinking concepts and language use in the GEMINI grant agreement. For example, the three phases of CIM have been renamed for GEMINI CIM. This is also presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 GEMINI Common Impact Model

3.2 GEMINI Common Impact Model

Just like the original CIM (see Petrovich et al., 2021), the GEMINI CIM considers user and community acceptance in the process of designing and implementing a new mobility solution through three steps. In the GEMINI CIM, these steps are labelled as 1) Inspiration, 2) Ideation, and 3) Implementation. For each step, specific tools for exploring and measuring user acceptance are provided.

An overview of the GEMINI CIM process and the tools associated with each step of the process is presented in Figure 2. This deliverable will next describe the three phases of the GEMINI CIM. The GEMINI CIM tools are presented separately in chapter 0.

Figure 2 Common Impact Model for NMS with Toolbox

Phase 1: Inspiration

The process starts with collecting input from key stakeholders. This includes identifying the potential mobility solution(s), relevant stakeholders and their roles, and the community's and stakeholders' features that influence acceptance of the mobility solution (e.g., values, priorities and practices, rational and emotional reactions to the proposed solution). Additionally, a stakeholder matrix is created to segment the stakeholders for better tailoring of potential user engagement activities.

Phase 2: Ideation

The findings from phase 1 are analysed and summarised to create an overview of the community's readiness to accept the mobility solution, their attitudes and emotional reactions towards the solution, and a ranking of perceived benefits, concerns, and barriers related to the solution. All these insights are then used to develop ideas and prototypes. Involving stakeholders and end-users in co-design, evaluation and testing of these ideas is key. This iterative process of testing and refining helps to avoid potential pitfalls in the implementation process and increases the likelihood of successful adoption of the new mobility solution.

Phase 3: Implementation

Before the final mobility solution is implemented, an engagement strategy is co-created with the local partner(s) to ensure that the service is well received by the community and meets their needs. The strategy should be based on insights about the community gathered in phases 1 and 2. Typical engagement activities include communication, events, incentives, and feedback mechanisms.

Some examples of activities that can be included in an engagement plan are:

- Test runs with user segments to ensure the solution is responding to the need.
- Onboarding sessions in different user segments to introduce the solutions and support users in registration or technical support for starting use.
- Meetings with stakeholders to share information about the solution and its benefits.
- Dissemination of information through various channels, such as newsletters, news articles, social media, and websites.

The engagement strategy should also include a plan for measuring the success of the service, such as tracking usage rates and customer satisfaction. This will allow the service provider to

make data-driven decisions and continuously improve the service to better meet the needs of the community.

The CIM is a dynamic model, meaning that after phase 3 is completed, phases 1 and 2 can and should be repeated over time to ensure the changing characteristics of the community are captured and considered in future engagement recommendations.

4 TOOLS FOR EXPLORING AND MEASURING USER ACCEPTANCE

4.1 Structure of the chapter

As described in the previous chapters of this deliverable, user acceptance is a key factor for the success of the new and shared mobility solutions of GEMINI. Understanding how different stakeholders perceive, accept, and adopt a proposed solution can help to design more effective and inclusive engagement strategies. Continuously evaluating user acceptance of the implemented mobility solutions enables data-driven decisions to continuously improve the service to better meet the needs of the community.

Therefore, it is important to have tools that can explore and measure user acceptance in a systematic and nuanced way. This chapter presents a set of tools that can help to assess user acceptance across the design and implementation of new and shared mobility solutions in GEMINI. The tools are based on the objectives and activities of each phase of the CIM and are presented following the CIM structure, as presented in Figure 2.

4.2 Tools for phase 1: Inspiration

The tools for phase 1 are designed to help the MLLs understand the context where the new and shared mobility solutions are implemented by providing insights into the needs, preferences, expectations, and concerns of different stakeholder groups. Insights from phase 1 will inform activities in phases 2 and 3.

4.2.1 Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder mapping is an exercise that involves identifying, analysing, and prioritizing individuals, groups, or organizations that may be affected by or have an impact on the project. This exercise helps identify and define relevant stakeholders who should be engaged throughout the project.

One approach to stakeholder analysis, suggested by the original CIM (Petrovich et al., 2021), is to segment stakeholders by positioning them in a matrix along two dimensions: influence in the implementation of the solution and interest in the solution. Different categories of stakeholders (e.g., for profit, non-for-profit, local authorities) can be distinguished with different colours. Relations between the stakeholders can be visualized with arrows.

At its most simple form, stakeholder mapping can be carried out as an exercise within the project team. These results can be enriched by also carrying out the exercise with important stakeholders to capture their view of actors that are relevant for the project. An example of questions to be asked during the exercise is provided in the table below.

Table 2 Discussion Guide Text for Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping discussion form
We'd like to identify the stakeholders who might be important for the successful implementation of [solution].
Please name the relevant stakeholders for the implementation of [solution] and then position each actor in a matrix, defined by two dimensions:
1. Influence on other stakeholders and in the decision process (someone whose advice has great influence would score high on influence)

2. Interest in the solution (someone who is enthusiastic about the solution would score high, someone who is expected to oppose score low).

[After placing each stakeholder, ask “why?” to get qualitative insights.]

Let’s look back at the stakeholder matrix that we compiled together:

- Which stakeholder do you meet or talk with at least once a week?
- Which stakeholder do you meet or talk with at least once a month?
- Are you and other stakeholders part of the same association, organization, board, club?
- Which stakeholders do you have a good relationship with?
- Do certain stakeholders have a close relationship with some of the others?

Figure 3 Example of Stakeholder Mapping

4.2.2 Questionnaire for contextual exploration

Understanding the context where the mobility solution is implemented is a crucial step in the beginning of the project. Exploring the context enables the project team to empathise with the potential end-users and stakeholders, and gain insights into their behaviours, attitudes, and expectations.

Table 3 provides a set of questions to guide exploration of the context where the new mobility solution is implemented. These questions can be used as guides in observing the context, as well as adapted to an interview guide or even a survey.

The questions presented in Table 3 are based on the COM-B model by Michie et al. (2011), which is a framework for analysing and designing behaviour change interventions. According to the COM-B model, behaviour is influenced by three key factors: Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation. By exploring these factors, the MLLs can uncover barriers and enablers for adopting their proposed new mobility solution.

Table 3 Content Exploration Questionnaire

Areas to explore	Examples of questions
<p>Capability Do community members have sufficient skills and knowledge to use NMS? What are the gaps?</p>	<p>Which transportation modes do the community members currently use?</p> <p>How familiar are they with NMS?</p> <p>How easy or difficult is it for the community members to use the digital tools and vehicles related to the NMS? How confident are the community members in their ability to use them?</p>
<p>Opportunity How can the social and physical environment help or hinder acceptance and use of NMS?</p>	<p>Is the NMS a controversial topic in the community? In what ways?</p> <p>Who/what are key information sources influencing views on mobility and NMS?</p> <p>To what extent do friends, family, or different communities help or hinder NMS use?</p> <p>Do the community leaders encourage NMS?</p> <p>What would be optimal locations for the NMS hubs/vehicles?</p> <p>Does the local infrastructure of the area help or hinder use of the NMS (e.g., public transportation, bike paths, parking spots)?</p> <p>Does using the NMS fit community members tasks/routines/needs?</p>
<p>Motivation Which attitudes, beliefs, values, and emotions help or hinder acceptance and use of NMS?</p>	<p>What kind of consequences do they think implementation of the NMS will have for them and their community? What would be the best and worst case scenarios?</p> <p>What emotions are linked to NMS?</p> <p>How difficult or easy do they think using the NMS is?</p> <p>Is using the NMS in line or against their identity and values?</p> <p>Do they trust the project team / NMS provider?</p>

4.2.3 Template for Mobility Living Lab Dashboard

The data collected in phase 1 is analysed and presented in a visual Solution Dashboard to help to quickly grasp the essential findings amongst partners and developers of the NMS. This dashboard can be easily converted into communication materials or used for stakeholder outreach purposes:

Figure 4 Illustration of Mobility Living Lab Dashboard

4.3 Tools for phase 2: Ideation

The ideation process includes co-design workshops and feedback iteration loops with the local stakeholders to assess the findings, enrich the analysis and feed into the development of the mobility solution or service.

Co-design workshops allow for the use of creative thinking techniques to collaboratively generate the prototype of the mobility solution. Several tools and techniques exist already and can be used in the workshop to support the ideation phase. We identified a selection of the co-design tools that are particularly relevant for designing the mobility solutions in Ceschin (2012) and in Cipriani(2021). They are summarised in the table below and presented in detail in Appendix A: Co-design tools. The selected tools are a mix of steering and visualisation tools and they collectively facilitate the formalization of the concept’s vision, structure the value chain, visualize stakeholder roles and interactions, and demonstrate sustainability benefits, thereby supporting the co-design of effective and sustainable mobility services and solutions. To be mentioned that the selection is not exhaustive and that there are many other co-design tools available in literature that are applicable to the mobility sector.

Co-design tools suggested for use in the GEMINI project are outlined in Table 4.

Table 4 Co-design Tools Relevant for Designing the Mobility Solutions

Tool	Description
Offering Diagram	Visualizes the functionalities delivered to customers/users, showcasing the core, basic, and added value functions along with sub-functions.
Personas	Personas represent typical users and their goals. Personas can be defined by dimensions that characterize and distinguish customer segments from one another. Persona dimensions are selected to inform the product or service experience under exploration.

Customer Journey Map	The customer journey map is a representation describing each step of the interaction that a user or customer has with a service, product, organization or system taking the perspective of the user.
Storyboard	Visualizes the functioning of the mobility solution over time, detailing the sequence of interactions between the customer/user and the solution designed.
Mobility Solution Elements	Illustrates the roles of each stakeholder in producing and delivering the mobility solution, visualizing both the material and non-material elements required.
Sustainability Diagram	Describes succinctly and effectively how the mobility concept achieves certain environmental and socio-ethical aims, visualizing the sustainability benefits derived from the solution.

Feedback sessions are also important as they may lead the data collection process to take new directions, if new open questions are raised. Ceschin (2012) describes the “Feedback Iteration Loop” as a critical component of the design process in the development of a product or a service. This iterative approach allows for the flexible evolution of the mobility concept, ensuring that it remains aligned with stakeholder needs, technological advancements, and contextual changes. The loop fosters a learning environment where experiments are not only about testing hypotheses but also about understanding and responding to the complex dynamics of socio-technical systems, enabling the iterative refinement of mobility innovations.

4.4 Tools for phase 3: Implementation

Phases 1 and 2 explore drivers and barriers of acceptance of NMS. In phase 3, the insights gathered in phases 1 and 2 are put into practice to facilitate acceptance of the implemented NMS through an engagement strategy. Section 4.4 provides guidelines for creation of an engagement strategy.

Once the mobility solution has been implemented, it is important to continuously evaluate its acceptance by the users and other stakeholders. This enables continuous improvement of the solution. Sections 4.4.2 and 4.4.3 provide both quantitative (survey template) and qualitative (interview guide) tools for evaluating acceptance of the implemented NMS. Quantitative evaluation enables large-scale data collection that can provide generalizable results that can be compared across different groups or time points. Qualitative evaluation can help contextualize the quantitative results by providing in-depth insights from users on their experiences and opinions about the solution, as well as their motivations and challenges. Both quantitative and qualitative evaluation are important for understanding the acceptance of a mobility solution, as they can complement each other and provide a more comprehensive picture of the phenomenon.

The methodology on how to do this is described in Deliverable 2.1, where the GEMINI evaluation framework and plan will be elaborated, including the monitoring of the awareness and acceptance by the different Mobility Living Labs.

4.4.1 Engagement strategy

The engagement strategy should include clear activities that are aimed at facilitating acceptance of the NMS and an associated timeline. The engagement strategy should build on the barriers and enabling factors identified in phases 1 and 2. In practice, the engagement activities can take the form of meetings, workshops, events, communication, and any other relevant

material and interaction. Chapter 3 provides inspiration for how the different drivers of NMS acceptance can be considered in the engagement activities.

Some of the examples of how the insights from phases 1 and 2 can be turned into engagement activities include:

- Consider what you have learned about the community. Activities that help address common community challenges can motivate local stakeholders to engage actively.
- Based on the motivations and knowledge level of the NMS's target group, messaging can be framed to be more appealing to them. For example, some target groups may be more drawn to the convenience of the NMS rather than the environmental benefits. An understanding of the general knowledge level and experience with similar solutions helps to help determine what type and level of support is needed.
- Existing social norms and comparison to other people and influencers in the community may help to motivate people to adopt NMS. Framing the messages based on what peers do or prefer may help to promote the NMS.

The documentation of the original Common Impact Model (E-LAND, 2022) provides great tools¹ and templates for creating an engagement plan.

4.4.2 Survey for evaluating user acceptance of implemented NMS

The survey items presented in Table 5 are based on the literature review presented in chapter , drawing from UTAUT2 constructs as well as other insights presented in the literature. These items will help develop a comprehensive picture of the drivers and barriers to acceptance of the NMS. Carrying out a survey with all the proposed items is typically not feasible and not even recommendable. The items are meant to provide inspiration and several options, and the final combination and wording of items should be adapted to each MLL's context.

Users of the NMS are an obvious target group for such a survey. The survey can be easily distributed through the NMS application or via SMS or e-mail. However, it's also important to consider people in the target group who haven't used the NMS. They can provide important perspectives on the barrier towards adopting the NMS. Reaching this segment isn't as easy, but it is important for compiling a complete picture about user acceptance of the NMS. The survey items presented in Table 5 are worded from the perspective of the NMS users, so for surveying non-users it's important to adjust the items to fit their point of view.

The questions in this table are indented as qualitative methods, but a scoring scale from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree) can be used in the survey to assess the answer for each statement:

¹E-LAND D2.5 https://elandh2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/ELAND_D2.5_v1.0_Submitted-approval-pending.pdf and online tools available on the E-LAND website <https://elandh2020.eu/knowledge-center/>

Table 5 User Acceptance Evaluation Survey Template

Survey template	
Topic	Survey items
Performance Expectancy	I find the NMS a useful mode of transport
	Using the NMS will help me reach my destination more quickly / conveniently
	Using the NMS to travel helps me to achieve things that are important to me
Effort Expectancy	I find the NMS easy to use
	Learning to use an NMS was easy for me
Social Influence	People who are important to me think that I should use the NMS
	In general, the authorities would support the use of the NMS
	In general, citizens of [target area] support having NMS
Facilitating conditions	I can get help when I have difficulties using the NMS
Hedonic motivation	Using the NMS is fun
	Using the NMS is enjoyable
Price value	The NMS is reasonably priced
	The NMS is a good value for the money
	At the current price, the NMS provides a good value
Safety	I feel safe when using NMS
	The NMS vehicles are in good and safe condition
	Road safety in [target location] allows me to feel safe when using the NMS

4.4.3 Interview guide for evaluating user acceptance of implemented NMS

Qualitative data can provide important insights to explain and expand the results of the quantitative evaluation of user acceptance (surveys). Interviews can provide rich and detailed insights into the users' perceptions, opinions, experiences, and preferences regarding the NMS, as well as the benefits and challenges they encounter when using it. Interviews can also help to identify any gaps or issues that may not be captured by the survey questions.

Table 6 provides a discussion guide of questions that can be used to qualitatively evaluate user acceptance of the NMS. The questions are not exhaustive and can be modified or adapted according to the specific context and objectives of the evaluation. Again, it is important to gather also qualitative insights from both people who have and haven't used the NMS to ensure a complete understanding of user acceptance.

Table 6 User Acceptance Deep Dive Discussion Guide

INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR USER ACCEPTANCE EVALUATION

1. Background information

- Tell me a little bit about yourself and your current life situation (e.g., age, family situation, employment)
- Tell me about your mobility habits.
 - What kind of trips do you do daily?
 - What about weekly or monthly?
 - What modes of transport do you usually use?

- Before the implementation of this NMS in your area, were you familiar with shared mobility solutions? Which ones? What impression did you have about shared mobility?

2. Personal experience with the NMS

Throughout this section, explore different divers of acceptance through follow-up questions related to usefulness, ease of use, social influences, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, price value, habits, safety, and environmental and health benefits.

- How familiar are you with the local NMS?
- Have you used it before?

Questions for participants who use NMS

- How did you learn about the NMS?
- What were the main reasons for you for trying the NMS?
- How often have you used the NMS since you first tried it?
 - What are their main reasons motivating you to use it?
- How satisfied are you with the NMS overall?
- What are the main benefits of using the NMS for you?
- What are the main drawbacks or challenges of using the NMS for you?
- Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when using the NMS?
 - If yes, what were they and how did you solve them?

Questions for participants who don't use NMS

- Could you describe why you haven't tried the NMS?
 - Have you ever considered trying it?
 - Why(not)?
- Is there anything that could make you consider trying the NMS?
- Are there any benefits you imagine the NMS could have for you?

3. NMS's impact on the community

- What do you think is the target group of the NMS?
 - Are you yourself part of the target group?
 - Does the NMS exclude some people? Who and why?
- How would you evaluate the introduction of the NMS to your community?
 - How successful/unsuccessful was it?
 - Why?
- How have people in this community reacted to the NMS?
 - What are some of the positive and negative comments you have heard?
 - Have the reactions evolved over time? How?
- In your view, has the use of the NMS evolved over time? How?
- What kind of consequences has the introduction of the NMS had for the community?
 - What have been the positive aspects of it?
 - What about negative aspects?
- How well do you think the NMS fits the local context? Why is that?
- Do you have any suggestions or feedback on how to improve the NMS or make it more accessible and appealing to more people?

5 CONCLUSION

In order to test acceptance of NMS, multiple tools must be used and these are summarised in the table below. The GEMINI CIM model suggests tools for the **Inspiration phase** such as a *Guide for questions to explore the context of a NMS* and a *Stakeholder mapping* to truly understand user needs and tailor services to the different stakeholders and the *Template for NMS Dashboard* that helps to visualise the results from the inspiration phase and is a valuable input in the co-design workshops in the next phase.

In the **Ideation phase** tools for *co-design workshops* are recommended to identify opportunities and generate ideas from a user centric approach, before testing and refining solutions with continuous feedback loops.

And last in the **Implementation phase** both a *Survey template* and *Interview guide* for evaluating user acceptance is suggested to evaluate final acceptance.

These templates can be used to gather data points that can be followed up by the NMS Dashboard for a visual follow up, for holistic understanding and coherent communication around how these datapoints interact. It is recommended for the MLLs to use the NMS Dashboard to follow progress throughout the different phases of the implementation (and not just in the inspiration phase), to ensure best possible processes and measures towards user acceptance.

PowerPoint templates for the user acceptance tools presented in this document are available upon request.

Table 7 Summary of User Acceptance Tools

User acceptance tools		
Phase	Tool	Purpose
Inspiration	Guide for questions to explore the context of a NMS	To understand the current situation, challenges, and opportunities for a NMS.
Inspiration	Stakeholder mapping	To identify and prioritize the different users and stakeholders of a NMS and their needs and expectations.
Ideation	Co-design workshops	To generate and evaluate ideas for a NMS from a user-centric perspective. Several tools can be also used in the co-design workshops. Some are suggested in section 4.4.
Implementation	Survey template	To measure the user satisfaction and acceptance of the final NMS.
Implementation	Interview guide	To collect qualitative feedback and insights from the users and stakeholders of the NMS.
Inspiration/ Ideation/ Implementation	Template for NMS Dashboard	To visualise the results from the inspiration phase and provide a valuable input for the co-design workshops. To be updated throughout the phases with new data inputs from the different phases.

REFERENCES

- Alshammari, S., & Rosli, M. S. (2020). *A Review of Technology Acceptance Models and Theories*. 4, 12–22.
- Andor, M., Gerster, A., Gillingham, K., & Horvath, M. (2020). Running a car costs much more than people think – stalling the uptake of green travel. *Nature*, 580, 453–455. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-01118-w>
- Casquero Soler, D., Monzón, A., García, M., & Martínez, O. (2022). Key Elements of Mobility Apps for Improving Urban Travel Patterns: A Literature Review. *Future Transportation*, 2, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/futuretransp2010001>
- Ceschin Fabrizio (2012). The introduction and scaling up of sustainable Product-Service Systems A new role for strategic design for sustainability. Politecnico di Milano. <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/56785?mode=complete>
- Cipriani Komatsu, Tamami (2021). SI methodologies for designing, prototyping, testing, monitoring. Deliverable 9.2 NetZeroCities. [D9.2.pdf\(netzerocities.eu\)](D9.2.pdf(netzerocities.eu))
- Curtale, R., Liao, F., & van der Waerden, P. (2021). User acceptance of electric car-sharing services: The case of the Netherlands. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 149, 266–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2021.05.006>
- Elmashhara, M. G., Silva, J., Sá, E., Carvalho, A., & Rezazadeh, A. (2022). Factors influencing user behaviour in micromobility sharing systems: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 27, 1–25. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2021.10.001>
- Fishman, E. (2016). Bikeshare: A Review of Recent Literature. *Transport Reviews*, 36(1), 92–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2015.1033036>
- Fleury, S., Tom, A., Jamet, E., & Colas-Maheux, E. (2017). What drives corporate car-sharing acceptance? A French case study. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 45, 218–227. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2016.12.004>
- Hazée, S., Delcourt, C., & Van Vaerenbergh, Y. (2017). Burdens of Access: Understanding Customer Barriers and Barrier-Attenuating Practices in Access-Based Services. *Journal of Service Research*, 20(4), 441–456. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670517712877>
- Jahanshahi, D., Tabibi, Z., & van Wee, B. (2020). Factors influencing the acceptance and use of a bicycle sharing system: Applying an extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 8(4), 1212–1223. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2020.08.002>
- Launonen, P., Salonen A. O., H. Liimatainen H. (2021) Icy roads and urban environments. Passenger experiences in autonomous vehicles in Finland, *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, Volume 80, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2021.03.015>
- Maas, B. (2022). Literature Review of Mobility as a Service. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)*(Vol. 14, Issue 14). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148962>

- Michie, S., van Stralen, M. M., & West, R. (2011). The behaviour change wheel: A new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions. *Implementation Science*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-6-42>
- Moeller, S., & Wittkowski, K. (2010). The burdens of ownership: reasons for preferring renting. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 20(2), 176-191. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604521011027598>
- Nansubuga, B., & Kowalkowski, C. (2021a). Car-sharing: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Journal of Service Management*, 32(6), 55-91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-10-2020-0344>
- Nansubuga, B., & Kowalkowski, C. (2021b). Car-sharing: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Journal of Service Management*, 32(6), 55-91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-10-2020-0344>
- Osswald, S., Wurhofer, D., Trösterer, S., Beck, E., & Tscheligi, M. (2012). *Predicting information technology usage in the car: towards a car technology acceptance model*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2390256.2390264>
- Pan, L., Xia, Y., Xing, L., Song, Z., & Xu, Y. (2022). Exploring Use Acceptance of Electric Bicycle-Sharing Systems: An Empirical Study Based on PLS-SEM Analysis. *Sensors*, 22(18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22187057>
- Pasca, M. G., Guglielmetti Mugion, R., Toni, M., Di Pietro, L., & Renzi, M. F. (2021). Gamification and service quality in bike sharing: an empirical study in Italy. *TQM Journal*, 33(6), 1222-1244. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-05-2020-0118>
- Petrovich, B., Murphy, B., Mikkelsen, T., & Kuivalainen, M. (2021). The Common Impact Model: A standardized methodology for community acceptance of decarbonized multivector local energy systems. *Ecocity World Summit 2021 Proceedings*.
- Slowik, P., & Kamakaté, F. (2017). *New mobility: Today's technology and policy landscape*.
- Tabourdeau, G., & Grange, C. (2020). From User Acceptance to Social Acceptance. *SIGHCI 2020 Proceedings*.
- Taherdoost, H. (2018). A review of technology acceptance and adoption models and theories. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 22, 960-967. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.03.137>
- Tamilmani, K., Rana, N. P., Wamba, S. F., & Dwivedi, R. (2021). The extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2): A systematic literature review and theory evaluation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 57, 102269. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102269>
- van Brecht, J., van Gent, M. J., & Renes, R. J. (2022). *CO2 reduction through shared mobility: A review of psychological factors for the switch from a private car to shared transport*.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425-478. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y. L., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer Acceptance and Use of Information Technology: Extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 157-178. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41410412>

Wüstenhagen, R., Wolsink, M., & Bürer, M. J. (2007). Social acceptance of renewable energy innovation: An introduction to the concept. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2683–2691. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.001>

Zhang, Y., & Kamargianni, M. (2023). A review on the factors influencing the adoption of new mobility technologies and services: autonomous vehicle, drone, micromobility and mobility as a service. *Transport Reviews*, 43(3), 407–429. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2022.2119297>

Other references

E-LAND (2022). D2.5 Final Common Impact Model (2022), available at https://elandh2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/ELAND_D2.5_v1.0_Submitted-approval-pending.pdf

GEMINI (2023). D1.1: Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers available at <https://www.geminiproject.eu/documents/>

APPENDIX A: CO-DESIGN TOOLS

A) OFFERING DIAGRAM

The offering diagram is used in the formalisation of the mobility concept to visualise which customers/users needs are fulfilled by it. In other words, it is a graphical representation aimed at visualising, in a synthetic form, which 'functionalities' are delivered to the users. It is basically a graphic representation, made up of images and text elements, showing:

- The core function: the function that characterizes the PSS;
- The basic functions: the functions required for the execution of the core function;
- The added value functions: functions associated with the core function able to increase and enrich its value;
- The sub-functions: which describe the way in which the functions will be delivered

Figure 5 Example of Offering Diagram from Ceschin (2012)

B) PERSONAS

Personas represent typical users and their goals. Personas can be defined by dimensions that characterize and distinguish customer segments from one another. Persona dimensions are selected to inform the product or service experience under exploration. To this end, they may include demographic information, attitudinal information (key drivers, triggers, or motivations), behavioural information (habits and practices, barriers, experiences sought, needs and desires), and information about desired outcomes or associated trends.

This range of selected personas frames the opportunity space so that NMS teams can focus on them for building concepts. Concepts are built to address the needs of these personas and to fit with their context. In order to accurately create personas, without merely wishful thinking, it is important to rely on in-depth qualitative (and quantitative) research.

<p>PICTURE</p>	<p>NAME</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>AGE</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>BEHAVIOUR</p> <input type="text"/>						
	<p>JOB TITLE</p> <input type="text"/>								
	<p>NEEDS</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>DIFFICULTIES & FRUSTRATIONS</p> <input type="text"/>							
<p>CITATION</p> <p>“</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>”</p>		<p>KEYWORDS</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>		
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<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>								

Figure 6 Personas template from Cipirani (2021)

C) THE CUSTOMER JOURNEY MAP

The customer journey map is a representation describing each step of the interaction that a user or customer has with a service, product, organization or system taking the perspective of the user. It can function as a planning- and strategic tool to keep the focus on the final users for the final development and the prototyping of a new solution. It can be also used to map existing systems to highlight pain points and opportunities for improvement. The tool has both the potential to develop new, user-centered solutions as well as improving existing services and systems by highlighting pain points and issues.

The Customer Journey creates an overview of the interaction of users with a product, service or system mapping their emotional state, touchpoints and needs across the journey. It helps to better understand critical points or opportunities, get in the users’ shoes and understand the effective use of touchpoints throughout the journey to deliver functioning and effective systems and services.

<p>User Actions</p> <p><i>What does the user do at each stage? Draw and/or describe the actions briefly</i></p>	<hr/> <hr/>	<hr/> <hr/>	<hr/> <hr/>	<hr/> <hr/>	<hr/> <hr/>
<p>User Needs</p> <p><i>What are the main needs of the user at that particular point?</i></p>	• <hr/> • <hr/> • <hr/>	• <hr/> • <hr/> • <hr/>	• <hr/> • <hr/> • <hr/>	• <hr/> • <hr/> • <hr/>	• <hr/> • <hr/> • <hr/>
<p>User Emotions</p> <p><i>What is the mood of the user in that step?</i></p>	😊 <input type="checkbox"/> 😐 <input type="checkbox"/> ☹ <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
<p>Touchpoints</p> <p><i>What are the points of contact between the user and the service/product provider?</i></p>					

Figure 7 Customer Journey Map template from Cipirani (2021)

D) STORYBOARD

The storyboard is used in the formalisation of the NMS concept to visualise the sequence of interactions between the customer/user and the NMS. The tool visualises the sequence of interactions occurring at front-desk level (interaction of user with the offer system), and at back-stage level (interactions between the various actors in producing and delivering the offer). Specifically, the aim of the tool is to describe and visualise the sequence of interactions and roles of the various actors (involved in the production and delivery of the offer) and the user.

Basically, the tool consists of a graphic representation showing:

- a sequence of images (accompanied by brief descriptions) showing the various interactions during the production and/or delivery of the NMS offer;
- an indication, for every interaction, of additional information (e.g. who the various actors involved are, their roles, etc.)

	CONCEPT DESIGN						DETAILED DESIGN					
KONE												
ACTIONS	KONE designs the concept of an intelligent, production-service system for green buildings, identifying the types of stakeholders to involve.	KONE designs the basic elements of products and services that could be included in the project.		KONE gets information about the specific context in which the building will rise and identifies the local stakeholders, including the client.	KONE presents the production-service system to the tenant, ready for building in a co-design process.	After the offer, KONE presents four modules: pay per function, collaboration in planning, maintenance, maintenance and environmental-friendly solutions.	After the selection, KONE details products and services to offer a highly efficient system. It's a maintenance-free pay per function offer that energy and environmental requirements.	Based on fixed costs and potential energy use reduction, KONE defines the design-contract (covering construction, "normal" maintenance and "pay per use")	KONE presents the project to the tenant and offers two pay per function long-term contracts: "normal" maintenance and "pay per use"			and with "free per night" KONE will pay for a part of the electricity used for energy.
Tenant												
ACTIONS			A company in USA, committed to sustainability, needs a new headquarters and announces the beginning of the planning stage of a new green building.			The tenant agrees about a "monthly" selection of the project proposed by KONE.					The tenant selects the "pay per use" option for will pay a sum in addition to the fixed costs, always lower than the energy cost. Not a standard solution.	
Facility manager												
ACTIONS												
End user												
ACTIONS												

Figure 8 Example of Storyboard from Ceschin (2012)

E) MOBILITY SOLUTION ELEMENTS

The tool is used in the formalisation of the NMS concept vision to describe the elements (material and non-material) required by the NMS, and which of the actors must design/produce/deliver these elements. The tool basically helps to define the roles of the individual actors in developing and delivering the NMS. It is basically a graphic representation, structured as a two-way table, where:

- the material (products, equipment, etc.) and non-material elements necessary to implement the PSS, are visualised along the horizontal axis. These elements are usually represented by pictograms;
- the actors involved in the system are visualised along the vertical axis;
- by crossing the elements with the actors the contribution made by the single actors in designing, producing and delivering the various elements is visualised

Figure 9 Example of Mobility Solution Elements from Ceschin (2012)

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